

Životní cyklus nových zdrojů energie (LiNES)

Horizon Europe Data Management Plan

2 February 2026

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Publication date	Changes
1.1	16 Apr 2025	update
1.2	1 Jul 2025	DublinCore standard added; Embargo information modified; Preexisting data management; README file use; Other scientific outputs added; Repositories added;
1.3	2 Feb 2025	Updated data formats, used datasets, data sharing policies, naming convention, Data storage

Contributors

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Projects

We will be working on the following project and for those are the data and work described in this DMP.

Lifecycle of New Energy Sources, Životní cyklus nových zdrojů energie

Acronym:

LiNES

Project Number:

CZ.02.01.01/00/23_020/0008508

Start date:

2024-09-01

End date:

2028-12-31

Funding:

Ministerstvo Školství, Mládeže a Tělovýchovy (Czechia):

CZ.02.01.01/00/23_020/0008508 (granted)

The project investigates new energy sources (NES) at several levels, from developing innovative technologies for energy storage and preventing risks associated with NES operation to managing NES as a source of secondary raw materials. With the expansion of new energy sources in the EU, a scientific problem arises in assessing safety, especially in the medium and long term. The project assesses the risks of NES to human health and safety, optimizes using these sources, and examines the economic and environmental impacts. It focuses on research into new materials, battery diagnostics, and incident prevention, innovative environmentally friendly processing of NES, and an overall assessment of the environmental impacts of NES.

1. Data Summary

Instrument datasets

In the LiNES project, a variety of instrument datasets will be acquired using laboratory and pilot-scale equipment. These datasets originate from measurement systems (e.g., sensors, test benches, spectrometers, simulation software, manufacturing/testing machines) and reflect a wide range of data types and formats, depending on the nature of the experiment and instrumentation.

Re-used datasets

In the LiNES project, the majority of datasets will be newly generated through experimental and computational activities. However, selected data from past R&D projects, student theses, and related institutional activities will be reused where relevant. These include internal datasets such as simulation models, software configuration profiles, experimental methodologies, report templates, process flow settings, and material property data developed by the consortium members.

The project builds upon the research and technological know-how of the participating institutions, which naturally involves partial reuse of previously generated and verified data.

Scientific publications (including review articles) are also considered a source of reused data, especially for comparative evaluation and contextual interpretation.

Where applicable, data from third parties, particularly from industrial and governmental partners (e.g., Ministry of the Environment – MŽP, CENIA, ECOBAT), may be used under agreed conditions. These data may include internal reports, datasheets, material flow statistics, or operational parameters. In such cases, datasets may not be publicly shareable due to confidentiality or business-sensitive content, though selected aggregated or anonymized outputs may be included in public deliverables upon agreement.

In addition, external datasets from literature and publicly available databases (e.g., GC/MS libraries, chemical databases such as NIST, SciFinder-n) will be used as background material to support experimental evaluation and data interpretation, not as standalone data products.

No harmonization of formats is necessary, as all reused data will be integrated at the level of internal use and pre-processed where needed.

Data formats and types

The project will involve a wide range of data types and formats, reflecting the diversity of scientific and technical activities across the partners. The table below summarizes the formats expected to be used in the project, together with their associated software tools and typical use cases.

Type	Format	Software	Use
Text document	*.txt	any	notes, logs, text data export, metadata
	*.doc(x)	MS Word	protocols, reports, methodology, internal documentation, literature research, publications etc.
	.pdf/.pdfa	Adobe reader etc.	final versions of reports and metedics, outputs for archivation, publications
	*.ppt(x)	MS Power Point	shared presentations
Tables	*.csv	MS Excel, LibreOffice aj.	data export and records
	*.xls(x)	MS Excel	calculations, tables, modelling outcomes
Images	*.jpeg	any	photo documentations etc.
	*.svg	Inkscape, Adobe Illustrator etc.	schemes, drawings, graphs, posters
	*.tiff	any	graphics, schemes
	*.png	any	photo documentations etc.
Video	*.mkv	VLC, WMP, KMPlayer aj.	experiment recordings
	*.mp4	VLC, WMP aj.	experiment recordings, conference recordings
	*.mxf	VLC, Adobe Premiere aj.	high-quality experiment recordings
Calculations	*.dat	ANSYS Fluent	simulation outputs
Simulations	*.cas	ANSYS Fluent	network, boundary conditions
	*.h5	ANSYS Fluent	complete model setup inc. Data
	*.cc7	CHEMCAD	simulation models
	*.csv	universal	general format for export for further processing
	*.png	universal	visual data export
	*.svg	universal	vector graphics
	.mpx/.mpj	Minitab	planned experiments outputs
CAD	.slm	Slice viewer	Data for LPBF machine manufacturing
	.magics	Materialise Magics	LPBF data preparation
Manu- facturing Testing	.ipt	Autodesk Inventor	models of exchangers, samples, sets etc.
	.sldprt; .sldasm	Solidworks	models of exchangers, samples, sets etc.
	.step	any CAD SW	neutral format for CAD model transfers in B-Rep representation
	.stl	any CAD SW	neutral format for CAD model transfers in triangular mesh
	.ntop	nTop	all complex CAD models including structured materials
	.dwg	any CAD SW	technical drawings for information transfer for conventional manufacturing
	.3mf	any SW for AM data preparation	universal format for data transfer for additive manufacturing
	.vtav	Trapezium X	universal testing machine SHIMADZU data format
Crystallogra- phy	.cif	Mercury	universal crystallography measurement format

This list includes both standardized formats suitable for long-term archiving and domain-specific formats necessary for internal processing and scientific evaluation.

We expect the total amount of data obtained and stored within the project to not exceed 5 TB.

Data storage

Within the project consortium, data will be stored in repositories maintained by each participating institution. Each partner is responsible for managing its own storage, with access restricted to authorized team members only, following the need-to-know principle. Access will take place exclusively through secure channels (VPN, SFTP, HTTPS). All repositories will be regularly backed up on separate servers to ensure recovery in case of system failure or data loss. Access rights will be managed by institutional administrators and reviewed on a regular basis. For data exchange between project partners, a secure cloud environment (e.g., CESNET Storage, Nextcloud, SharePoint, or a comparable platform with controlled access) will be used. This approach ensures both the protection of sensitive information and efficient collaboration among project participants. Additionally, the collaborating parties use a network attached storage (NAS), which is a local cloud network for sharing, storing and archiving data. Another central NAS network will be purchased and operated specifically for the purpose of this project and is most used to store most of the processed and available data pertaining to this project.

Institutional Specifics of BUT (Brno University of Technology): Data will be stored on institutional storage systems managed by each project partner (e.g., university servers, SharePoint/OneDrive folders, NAS systems). Access to these systems is limited to authorized users through institutional credentials.

Sensitive or unpublished data will remain in secure internal storage and will be shared only as needed.

Data exchange between project partners will be enabled through secure cloud environments (e.g., CESNET Storage, Nextcloud, SharePoint), and all data will be regularly backed up in accordance with institutional policies.

Public datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories such as ASEP (Czech Academy of Sciences) or Zenodo, depending on the nature and origin of the data.

Potential use outside the project

We believe that data related to LiNES project could be potentially used by policy makers and public authorities dealing with sustainability and risk management of new energy sources. Publicly shareable datasets will be made available through open repositories (e.g., Zenodo, ASEP) in accordance with FAIR principles and IPR restrictions.

Aggregated, anonymized, or derived data may also be shared with third parties upon request or as part of public project deliverables.

2. FAIR Data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To ensure consistency, traceability, and long-term usability of project data, a unified file naming convention will be applied across all participating institutions. The convention follows a structured format:

[Creator]_[Title]_[Date]_[Type]_[Version].[Format]

- **Creator:** Abbreviation of the institution, research team or an operator (e.g., ICPF, UCT, VUT).
- **Title:** Short descriptive title of the dataset/file, without diacritics and spaces (underscores _ as separators).
- **Date:** Date of file creation in the format YYYYMMDD.
- **Type:** Nature of the file (e.g., raw, processed, analysis, report).
- **Version:** Version number in the format v01, v02, ensuring that older versions are never overwritten.
- **Format:** File extension following MIME standards (e.g., csv, xlsx, pdf).

All project partners are required to apply this naming convention consistently. Files must not contain diacritics, spaces, or special characters, and underscores (_) must be used as separators. Dates must always be written in full (YYYYMMDD). Versioning is mandatory to prevent data loss or overwriting.

This convention will allow datasets to be easily identified, properly archived, and reliably reused, while ensuring alignment with FAIR principles.

In addition, metadata will be created for all datasets designed for publication or open sharing. These will follow the Dublin Core standard or the template required by the target repository (e.g., ZENODO). The format will be mandatory in all metadata records:

[Identifier]_[Creator]_[Title]_[Date]_[Type]_[Format]_[Language]_[Rights].[Format]

- **Identifier:** A unique identifier for the dataset or file (LiNES).
- **Title:** Short descriptive title of the dataset/file, without diacritics and spaces (underscores _ as separators).
- **Creator:** Name of the institution or research team responsible for the dataset.
- **Date:** Dates recorded (YYYYMMDD).
- **Type:** Specification of the nature of the data (e.g., raw, processed, analysis, report).
- **Format:** File format, expressed using MIME types (e.g., text/csv, application/pdf).
- **Language:** Language code according to ISO 639-1 (e.g., cs, en).
- **Rights:** Information about licensing and usage conditions (e.g., CC BY 4.0).

Supporting information for publications (published) will be published on the website of the Publisher and/or on the repositories such as **ASEP**

(<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100014032>) or **ZENODO**

(<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010468>).

- The dataset will receive a digital object identifier (DOI) A persistent identifier will be assigned by the repository. The repository will make sure that the persistent identifier can be attached to a digital object. The availability of the data is maintained by the repository.

There are the following 'Minimal Metadata About ...' (MIA...) standards for our experiments:

- [Dublin Core Metadata Element Set](#) (DCES)

Therefore, in addition to consistent file naming, each dataset intended for publication or sharing will be accompanied by structured metadata records, which will include:

- Dataset title,
- Full names and ORCID of creators,
- Publication date,
- Publisher or responsible institution,
- Version,
- License (e.g.m CC BY 4.0),
- Persistent identifier (DOI assigned by the repository),
- Dataset keywords,
- Description of data content, structure, units etc.,
- Type of publication (if applied),
- Access conditions and embargo information (if applied).

Metadata will be created within the chosen repository (e.g., ZENODO, ASEP) to ensure compliance with FAIR principles and machine-readability.

In addition, local metadata files (e.g., readme.txt) will be maintained for all datasets describing variables, measurement conditions, units and tools used.

These will aid in re-use and long-term interpretability, even for data not intended for public dissemination.

2.2. Making data accessible

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data. Data that is not legally restrained or sensitive will be released no later than at the time of publication of the corresponding scientific outputs.

Legally restrained intellectual property data will be stored and made public when agreed upon by the collaborating teams.

Metadata will be openly available with instructions on how to get access to the data. Metadata will be available in a form that can be harvested and indexed and managed by the used repository/repositories.

We have a consortium agreement that arranges Intellectual Property.

For our produced data, conditions are as follows:

Data that can be made public will be placed on one of the following repositories and assigned a persistent identifier (such as DOI):

ASEP – Repository of Czech Academy of Sciences (Repozitář ASEP)
<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100014032>. The distribution will be available under the following license: Starting 2024-09-01: Freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY).

ZENODO – EU Open Research repository
(<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010468>). The distribution will be available under the following license: Starting 2024-09-01: Freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY).

A user of this data can use it without any specific software, or, any special software needed to access and use the data will be described in a accompanying README file.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Some of the research will use data previously existing in the independent research of the partners involved in the project. These were obtained using established procedures and as such will have no problems with interoperability and integration into the new datasets.

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- [Rich Text Format](#) (RTF) It is a standardized format.
- [Document management -- Electronic document file format for long-term preservation -- Part 1: Use of PDF 1.4 \(PDF/A-1\)](#) (ISO 19005-1:2005) It is a standardized format.
- [Comma-separated Values](#) (CSV) It is a standardized format.
- [Tagged Image File Format](#) (TIFF) It is a standardized format.
- [Joint Photographic Experts Group Format](#) (JPEG Format)
It is a standardized format.
- [Crystallographic Information Framework](#) (CIF) It is a standardized format.

We will be using the following standards (encodings, terminologies, vocabularies, ontologies):

- [IUPAC Compendium of Chemical Terminology](#) (IUPAC Gold Book)
- [Chemical Entities of Biological Interest](#) (ChEBI)

2.4. Increase data re-use

To ensure accuracy, reliability, and reusability of project data, quality assurance (QA) processes will be implemented throughout the entire data lifecycle. QA measures will start at the point of

collection, where data entry will be validated through predefined formats, mandatory fields, and, where appropriate, automated validation scripts.

During data processing, original raw data will always be preserved, and any cleaning or transformation steps will be documented and versioned.

Metadata quality will be assured by applying standardized schemas (e.g., Dublin Core) and verifying that all mandatory fields are completed. File and metadata naming conventions will be applied consistently to ensure traceability.

Prior to data sharing or publication, datasets will undergo internal review by project team members, and, if necessary, external review to confirm correctness and completeness, typically done by the Data Steward. Automated tools and repository-specific validators can be used to check file formats and compliance with FAIR principles.

This comprehensive quality assurance approach ensures that project data are trustworthy, consistent, and suitable for long-term preservation and reuse.

Additionally, to increase data re-use, we will use open formats (csv, txt etc.), provide rich metadata, apply controlled vocabularies and supply detailed data documentation. We will use clear and permissive licences (e.g., CC BY), trusted repositories (*vide supra*) and assign persistent identifiers where applicable. The published data sets will be accompanied by a README.txt file, which will contain information about the contents of the datasets, how to open, use and interpret them and any additional information that could be relevant.

3. Other research outputs

The project is expected to generate **patents (P)**, **utility models (F_{uzit})**, **functional samples (G_{funk})** and **specialized maps (N_{map})** that maybe patented.

4. Allocation of resources

The project allocates 0.1 FTE to a data steward, who will be responsible for overseeing the implementation of the Data Management Plan, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles, coordinating metadata creation, and monitoring data quality assurance processes. No additional financial allocation is made for data management activities beyond staff time.

Martin Jakubec serves as the project Data Steward. He is responsible for the management and proficiency of data including data processing, data policies, data guidelines, and data availability.

All data management activities, including preparing data for publication, creating metadata, anonymising data where applicable, curating data and disseminating it, will be carried out within the capacities described above of the host institution, in close cooperation with researchers from partner institutions. No additional specialist expertise is required to implement the Data Management Plan.

FAIR principles are a central component of the project's data management approach and are considered throughout the entire data lifecycle. The project team applies FAIR data practices internally to ensure efficient use, transparency, and reusability of research data.

The project Lifecycle of New Energy Sources (Životní cyklus nových zdrojů energie, CZ.02.01.01/00/23_020/0008508) relies on the existing capacities of institutional hardware and software. Additionally, a central project data storage with a capacity of 5 TB has been established using the project resources at the coordinating institution (ÚCHP). This centralized storage serves as a hub for storing research data, milestones documentation, publications, and other project outputs, ensuring secure data sharing among consortium members.

Data storage, backup, and long-term preservation will be provided using existing institutional infrastructure and repositories, which are available to the project and do not charge usage fees. No additional hardware or software acquisitions are required. None of the used repositories charge for their services. Consequently, no project funds are allocated for repository fees, storage solutions, software licenses, or outsourced services.

Standard costs for Open Access publishing (APCs) are covered by the project budget.

5. Data security

Project members can carry data with them on password-protected laptops. All computers are to be protected with a password. All data centers where project data is stored carry sufficient certifications. All used network services used for sharing and distributing data will be secured. All web services are addressed via secure HTTP (<https://...>). Remote access to infrastructure will be achieved via secure VPN. Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

Data stored on internal HW will be frequently backed up and transferred to secure institutional storages. Institutional storages are regularly backed up on duplicate servers, so the possible impact to the project or organization if information is lost is minimal.

The possible impact to the project or organization if information is leaked is minimized by using password protection wherever possible. Only workers involved in an official capacity will be allowed access to the data. If necessary, non-disclosure agreements will be used to avoid leakage. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is vandalised is small due to the above.

We are not using any personal information.

We are running the project in a collaboration between different groups and institutes. A collaboration agreement that describes who can have access to what data in the project is set. For this purpose a central project data storage with a capacity of 5 TB has been established at the coordinating institution (ÚCHP). This centralized storage serves as a hub for storing research data, milestones documentation, publications, and other project outputs, ensuring secure data sharing among consortium members.

The unpublished data will be stored on the internal storage facilities of the respective research groups and will be shared between the interested parties upon request. The published data will be stored on selected repositories according to the preferences of the respective partners. The repositories will be selected from:

ASEP - Repository of Czech Academy of Sciences ASEP

<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100014032>.

ZENODO – Open Science repository

<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010468>.

6. Ethics

Data we produce

For the data we produce, the ethical aspects are as follows: It does not contain personal or ethically sensitive data of any kind.

Data we collect

We will not collect any personal data. The data collection is not subject to ethical legislation.

7. Other issues

We use the [FAIR Wizard](https://www.fair-wizard.com/wizard) with its *CAS Common DSW Knowledge Model* (ID: 053avzc18:CAScommon:3.0.3) knowledge model to make our DMP. More specifically, we use the <https://avcr.fair-wizard.com/wizard> FAIR Wizard instance where the project has direct URL: <https://avcr.fair-wizard.com/wizard/projects/8b05055ba4c7-4fbe-95d7-59fdacf76e96>.

We will be using the following policies and procedures for data management:

- **Open Science Principles of the Czech Academy of Sciences**

<https://www.avcr.cz/en/about-us/legal-regulations/open-science-principles-ofthe-czech-academy-of-sciences/>

As our institute does not yet have its own institutional open science policy, we currently adhere to the "Open Science Principles of the Czech Academy of Sciences".